

Review of ‘Dynamical Learning of Dynamics’, [arXiv:1902.02875 \[q-Bio\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/1902.02875)

By Dr Bheemaiah, Anil Kumar, A.B, bheemaiaha@yopmail.com

Review Summary.

Abstract.

The ability of humans and animals to quickly adapt to novel tasks is difficult to reconcile with the standard paradigm of learning by slow synaptic weight modification. Here we show that already static neural networks can learn to generate required dynamics by imitation. After appropriate weight pretraining, the networks dynamically adapt to learn new tasks and thereafter continue to achieve them without further teacher feedback. We explain this ability and illustrate it with a variety of target dynamics, ranging from oscillatory trajectories to driven and chaotic dynamical systems.

what:

learning to learn in recurrent networks with continuous input and outputs, learning dynamical behaviors.

how:

model:

Network model. We use recurrent neural networks, where each neuron (or neuronal subpopulation) i , $i = 1, \dots, N$, is characterized by an activation variable $x_i(t)$ and communicates with other neurons via its firing rate $r_i(t)$, which is a nonlinear function of $x_i(t)$ [1, 2]. The net-work has two outputs, which can be interpreted as linear neurons: a signal output $z_k(t)$, $k = 1, \dots, N_z$, and a context output $c_l(t)$, $l = 1, \dots, N_c$ (Fig. 1). Their weights are the only plastic ones. After learning, $z(t)$ generates the desired dynamics while $c(t)$ indexes it. They are continually fed back to the network, allowing their autonomous generation [31]. During learning, our networks are temporarily also informed about their output’s difference from the

target $\tilde{z}(t)$ by an error input $\varepsilon(t) = z(t) - \tilde{z}(t)$. When this input is absent, we set $\varepsilon(t) = 0$ and the output of $c(t)$ to a constant value. In isolation $x_i(t)$ decays to zero with a time constant τ_i that combines the decay times of membrane potential and synaptic currents. Unless mentioned otherwise, we set $\tau_i = 1$ fixing the overall time scale. Taken together, for constant weights the network dynamics are given by

$$\tau \dot{x}(t) = -x(t) + Ar(t) + w_{zz}(t) + w_{cc}(t) + w_{\varepsilon\varepsilon}(t) + w_{uu}(t), \quad (1)$$

$$z(t) = ozr(t), \quad c(t) = ocr(t), \quad (2)$$

with recurrent weights A , the diagonal matrix of time constants τ , signal and context output weights oz and oc , feedback weights w_z , w_c and input weights w_{ε} , w_u . We choose $r_i(t) = \tanh(x_i(t) + b_i)$ [29, 31, 32], where b_i is a constant offset breaking the $x \rightarrow -x$ symmetry without input.

Learning of target signal $z(t)$ using the difference $\tilde{z}(t) - z(t)$, examples of sinusoidal, superposition of sines and a fixed point.

Why:

modeling of natural systems, with applications in physical systems and in computational physics, circuit design and phenomenology.

So What:

dynamical learning, useful in biomorphic designs, a new paradigm of computing, analogous to BEAM? but with dynamical learning of learning.

Criticism:

Biomorphic computing is dynamic programming, but with simplified supervision in error signals, there are two alternatives to associative learning, GAN based discriminators and noise synthesis in a feedback loop, and the learning in bifurcation dynamics with a DC to DC converter as an example.

In the context of pulse codes, ("Wolfram Cloud Page" n.d.) could we create an NLP learning and a VUI, (Abbott 2002; Singh, Ramasubramanian, and Shivam 2019) with such dynamical learning?

could we use dialog templates as an alternative to BEAM designs in MFA II (Bheemaiah, n.d.) (Bheemaiah, n.d.) with functoid algebras? and state learning as stability systems, is this a variation of

BEAM, with fixed point computing, bifurcation dynamics and knowledge management in phase transitions in ergodic transitions to fixed-point dynamics, a possible internal representation and in hidden variables? much like Bohm theories?(Bohm 1962)(Bohm 1962; Aaronson 2005; Bell and Aspect, n.d.; Bell 1988; Pladevall and Mompert 2019)

References.

- C. Klos, Y. F. K. Kossio, S. Goedeke, **A. Gilra**, and R.-M. Memmesheimer. ‘Dynamical Learning of Dynamics’. [arXiv:1902.02875 \[q-Bio\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/1902.02875), 2019.
- Aaronson, Scott. 2005. “Quantum Computing and Hidden Variables.” *Physical Review A*. <https://doi.org/10.1103/physreva.71.032325>.
- Abbott, Ken. 2002. “VUI Design Principles and Techniques.” *Voice Enabling Web Applications: VoiceXML and Beyond*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4302-0850-1_8.
- Bell, J. S. 1988. *Speakable and Unspeakable in Quantum Mechanics*. Cambridge University Press.
- Bell, J. S., and Alain Aspect. n.d. “On the Problem of Hidden Variables in Quantum Mechanics.” *Speakable and Unspeakable in Quantum Mechanics*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9780511815676.003>.
- Bheemaiah, Anil Kumar. n.d. “Beam Auto Pilot.” <https://doi.org/10.35543/osf.io/e3njs>.
- . n.d. “Taskoids: A Formal Definition.” <https://doi.org/10.31224/osf.io/yhsbt>.
- Bohm, D. 1962. “Hidden Variables in the Quantum Theory.” *Radiation and High Energy Physics*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-1-4832-2910-2.50013-x>.
- Pladevall, Xavier Oriols, and Jordi Mompert. 2019. *Applied Bohmian Mechanics: From Nanoscale Systems to Cosmology*. CRC Press.
- Singh, Abhishek, Karthik Ramasubramanian, and Shrey Shivam. 2019. “Introduction to Microsoft Bot, RASA, and Google Dialogflow.” *Building an Enterprise Chatbot*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4842-5034-1_7.
- “Wolfram Cloud Page.” n.d. Accessed November 8, 2019. <https://www.wolframcloud.com/obj/6265d36a-4ba6-49d0-ad36-e0449f6efd3a>.